

Appendix - Designing Conversational AI to Support Think-Aloud Practice in Technical Interview Preparation for CS Students

APPENDIX

A. Implementation Notes

The tool is implemented as a web application using the VueJS framework [1], along with HTML, CSS, and TypeScript. The backend components are built using the Flask framework [2] with Python. For all LLM usage in the tool, we use OpenAI's GPT-4o-mini [3] due to its low latency [3] and good performance [4], making it suitable for conversational AI implementation in our tool. For the speech-to-text model, we use the Web Speech API [5] to convert users' voice input into text, which is then fed into the LLM to generate responses. We use OpenAI's "tts-1" text-to-speech model [6] to convert the text responses into audio output.

Our system uses a manual turn-taking mechanism during the technical interview simulation, where users must either use a keyboard shortcut "Ctrl + M" or press the "Get Response" button to end their speaking turn and receive an AI response. We chose this simple approach because our primary focus is on understanding how users perceive the use of conversational AI in supporting think-aloud practice, rather than finding the best turn-taking mechanisms in this context. We acknowledge that future research could explore this mechanism further.

B. Prompts

1) Prompts for Interview Simulation:

a) *Prompt for the First Interviewer Message:* You are a hiring manager conducting a coding interview. Your goal is to assess the candidate's problem-solving skills, coding ability, and communication. Begin by greeting the candidate and presenting the following coding problem.

Problem:

[input problem]

b) *Prompt for the Rest of the Interviewer Interaction:*

You are a hiring manager conducting a coding interview. Your goal is to assess the candidate's problem-solving skills, coding ability, and communication. Ensure that your communication is short and concise. Provide hints only if the candidate is stuck, but avoid giving too many hints, especially those that reveal the solution.

The coding problem is the following:

[input problem]

The candidate will implicitly follow these six steps:

- 1) **Understanding:** The candidate may ask clarifying questions to ensure they fully understand the problem and may propose an initial test case to demonstrate their understanding of the requirements.
- 2) **Initial Ideation:** The candidate will brainstorm initial ideas on how to solve the problem.
- 3) **Idea Justification:** The candidate will justify their approach, explaining why the chosen solution is suitable.
- 4) **Implementation:** The candidate will code the solution while thinking aloud to describe their thought process.
- 5) **Review (Dry Run):** After coding, the candidate will dry-run their code with a test case, walking through the logic step by step.
- 6) **Evaluation:** The candidate will evaluate their solution, discussing possible optimizations, edge cases, and any necessary improvements.

Throughout the interview:

- Prompt the candidate to think aloud and explain their reasoning at each step.
- Ask follow-up questions to gauge their understanding and depth of knowledge.
- Provide hints only if the candidate is stuck, but avoid giving too many hints, especially those that reveal the solution.
- Ignore minor typos or grammar errors in the candidate's responses.
- Keep your communication short and concise.

At any point, you may refer to the candidate's current code (ignoring syntax errors and focusing on the logic):

Candidate's Current Code:

[Code]

Make sure your communication is short and concise.

[APPEND CONVERSATION]

2) *Prompt for AI-Feedback:* I have a transcript of a coding interview where the interviewee is required to think aloud while solving a problem. Based on the transcript provided below, please give detailed feedback on the interviewee's performance, focusing on the following six aspects. Format the response in JSON using the following structure:

– "understanding" : "Feedback on how the interviewee demonstrated their understanding of the problem by

asking clarifying questions and/or proposing a test case.”,
 ”initial ideation”: ”Feedback on how the interviewee brainstormed and proposed their initial ideas.”,
 ”idea justification”: ”Feedback on how the interviewee justified their proposed approach and explain the walk through of their idea.”,
 ”implementation”: ”Feedback on how the interviewee communicated their thought process while coding the solution.”,
 ”review dry run”: ”Feedback on how the interviewee performed a dry run of their code, explaining the execution flow using test cases.”,
 ”evaluation”: ”Feedback on how the interviewee evaluated their solution, including discussions of potential optimizations, edge cases, or improvements.”

Make sure your feedback is constructive and suggests things that they need to improve for each section. Please also ignore typos or transcription errors.

Here are the specific phases to assess:

- 1) **Understanding:** Evaluate whether the interviewee correctly expressed their understanding of the question by asking relevant clarifying questions and illustrating with a sample test case. Did they fully grasp the requirements? Were there missed opportunities to seek more clarity?
- 2) **Initial Ideation:** Assess how the interviewee brainstormed initial ideas and solutions. It is acceptable if candidates start with a brute-force solution and then optimize their ideas gradually. Did they consider multiple approaches or stick with a single idea? Did they clearly explain their thought process?
- 3) **Idea Justification:** Evaluate how well the interviewee justified their solution and walk through their solution before implementing it. Did they explain why their approach was suitable or compare it to alternative solutions? Were they able to defend their choice of data structures, algorithms, or logic?
- 4) **Implementation:** Provide feedback on how well the interviewee communicated their thought process while coding. Was their reasoning easy to follow? Were there gaps in their explanation or places where communication became unclear?
- 5) **Review (Dry Run):** Analyze how the interviewee performed a dry run of their code with a test case. Did they clearly explain the flow of execution, identify potential issues, or spot logical errors?
- 6) **Evaluation:** Provide feedback on how the interviewee evaluated their solution after coding. Did they discuss possible optimizations or improvements?

If the interviewee did not perform a phase, note that it was not done. Make sure your feedback is constructive and that

you ignore typos or transcription errors.

Transcript:

[transcript]

3) *Prompt for AI-Generated Example Dialogue:* Simulate a realistic coding interview between an interviewer and an interviewee focused on solving the given problem. The simulation should include explanations of best practices based on the example provided. When writing the code, present it as ”lines of code” and provide step-by-step explanations. Avoid using built-in libraries if possible.

Format your response in JSON format:

```
[
  -
    "role (interviewer/interviewee)": "",
    "content": "",
    "code (containing STEP-BY-STEP code that the interviewee writes while thinking aloud)": "",
    "explanation (explain the importance or rationale of answering in such a way)": ""
  ,
  ...
]
```

The interviewer may implicitly ask probing questions to understand the interviewee’s thought process, while the interviewee should clearly explain their approach, consider edge cases, and write code to solve the problem. The interviewer may offer hints if the interviewee gets stuck.

The interviewee should think aloud, ask clarifying questions if needed, and demonstrate their problem-solving skills.

Problem: {input problem}

The interview should implicitly follow these six steps:

- 1) **Understanding:**
 - The interviewer introduces the problem and provides examples.
 - The interviewee may ask clarifying questions to ensure a full understanding of the problem.
 - The interviewee may propose an initial test case to demonstrate their understanding of the requirements.
- 2) **Initial Ideation:**
 - The interviewee brainstorms initial ideas on how to solve the problem.
- 3) **Idea Justification:**
 - The interviewee justifies their chosen approach, explaining why it is suitable for the problem.
 - The interviewee explains the walkthrough of the solution
- 4) **Implementation:**
 - The interviewee writes the code to solve the problem, explaining their logic as they go.
 - The interviewer may ask the interviewee to consider different cases, such as empty inputs or edge scenarios.

5) Review (Dry Run):

- After coding, the interviewee dry-runs their code with provided examples, walking through the logic step by step.
- The interviewee considers additional test cases to ensure robustness.

6) Evaluation:

- The interviewee evaluates their solution, discussing possible optimizations, edge cases, and any necessary improvements.
- The interviewer provides feedback on the solution, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement.
- The interviewee reflects on their performance and discusses what they could have done differently.

C. Participant Demographics

TABLE I: Participant Demographics

ID	Gender	Age	Occupation	Race and Ethnicity	Interview Count
P1	Male	32	PhD Student	Asian	> 10
P2	Male	20	4th Year Undergrad	Middle Eastern	1-5
P3	Female	26	PhD Student	Middle Eastern	1-5
P4	Female	25	PhD Student	Asian	1-5
P5	Female	21	4th Year Undergrad	Asian	1-5
P6	Male	20	3rd Year Undergrad	White	1-5
P7	Male	20	3rd Year Undergrad	Asian	1-5
P8	Male	20	3rd Year Undergrad	Asian	1-5
P9	Male	20	3rd Year Undergrad	White	1-5
P10	Male	19	3rd Year Undergrad	Asian	1-5
P11	Female	22	4th Year Undergrad	Asian	6-10
P12	Male	20	3rd Year Undergrad	White	6-10
P13	Female	21	4th Year Undergrad	Asian	6-10
P14	Male	24	PhD Student	White & Hispanic/Latino	0
P15	Female	22	4th Year Undergrad	White	0
P16	Female	20	3rd Year Undergrad	White	0
P17	Male	21	4th Year Undergrad	White	1-5

*Note: "Interview Count" refers to the number of technical interviews the participant has completed before this study.

D. Coding Tasks for Technical Interview Simulation

Our technical interview practice tool includes two coding questions for users to choose from. These tasks are adapted from common data structure/ algorithm problems on LeetCode [7], which are typical in technical interviews [8]. We selected problems that have multiple valid solution approaches, which aligns with our focus on practicing the think-aloud technique, where users explain their thought processes while navigating their solutions. Following guidelines from prior works on technical interview practice [9], [10], we ensured that the selected tasks were solvable within a reasonable time limit for the user study and neither too trivial nor overly complex. These are the coding tasks:

1) *Problem 1. Intersection of Two Arrays:* Given two integer arrays `nums1` and `nums2`, return an array of their intersection. Each element in the result must appear as many times as it shows in both arrays, and you may return the result in any order.

a) *Example 1:*

Input: $\text{nums1} = [1,2,2,1]$, $\text{nums2} = [2,2]$

Output: $[2,2]$

b) *Example 2:*

Input: $\text{nums1} = [4,9,5]$, $\text{nums2} = [9,4,9,8,4]$

Output: $[4,9]$

Sample Solution 1. Using a Hash Map

- Intuition: Use a hash map to count the occurrences of each number in the first array. Then, iterate through the second array to identify common elements. For each element in the second array, check if it exists in the hash map. If it does, add the element to the result array and decrement its occurrence count in the hash map.
- Time Complexity: $O(n + m)$
- Memory Complexity: $O(n + m)$

Sample Solution 2. Sorting and Two Pointer (Optimizing The Space)

- Intuition: To find the common elements between two arrays, start by sorting both arrays. Then, use two pointers, one for each array, beginning at their respective starting positions. These pointers initially point to the smallest elements in each array. Compare the elements at the two pointers: if they are the same, add the element to the result array and move both pointers forward by one. If the elements are different, increment the pointer pointing to the smaller element, as this ensures we progress toward finding potential matches.
- Time Complexity: $O(n \log n + m \log m)$
- Memory Complexity: $O(\min(n, m))$ (There is no need for additional space for Hash Map)

2) *Problem 2. Two Sum:* Given an array of integer nums and an integer target , return indices of the two numbers such that they add up to the target. You cannot use the same element twice. You can return the answer in any order.

a) *Example 1:*

Input: $\text{nums} = [2,7,11,15]$, $\text{target} = 9$

Output: $[0,1]$

Sample Solution 1. Two-pass Hash Table

- Intuition: First, precompute a hash table by iterating through the first array, where each element is added as a key and its index as the value. Then, iterate through the second array. For each element, check if the target complement ($\text{target} - \text{nums}[i]$) exists in the hash table. If it does, return the index of the current element and the index of its complement.
- Time Complexity: $O(n)$
- Memory Complexity: $O(n)$

Sample Solution 2. Sorting + Binary Search

- Intuition: The algorithm to solve the Two Sum problem using sorting and binary search involves first pairing each number with its original index and sorting the array by values. Then, for each number in the sorted array, it computes the complement needed to reach the target and performs a binary search in the remaining portion of the

array to find this complement. If the complement is found, the original indices of the two numbers are returned.

- Time Complexity: $O(n \log n)$
- Memory Complexity: $O(n)$

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